

Errata for “Cost of quantum entanglement simplified” and “Exact entanglement cost of quantum states and channels under PPT-preserving operations”

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(Dated: April 24, 2024)

The exact entanglement cost under quantum operations that completely preserve positivity of the partial transpose (PPT) was shown to be given by the κ -entanglement, which was claimed to be additive under tensor products. In this erratum, we construct a counterexample to additivity, thus proving instead that the κ -entanglement is non-additive. This implies that the exact entanglement cost under PPT operations is instead given by the regularized κ -entanglement. We also prove that a quantity defined by Lami is a single-letter SDP lower bound on the regularized κ -entanglement, which leads to a sufficient condition for the κ -entanglement to be equal to the exact entanglement cost under PPT operations. We make similar arguments for the κ -entanglement of quantum channels: we prove that the exact parallel simulation cost is equal to the regularized κ -entanglement of channels, the sequential simulation cost of quantum channels is bounded from above by the κ -entanglement of channels and from below by the regularized κ -entanglement of channels and a new single-letter SDP quantity related to the aforementioned one defined for states. Here we also present a numerical counterexample to additivity for κ -entanglement of channels.

I. INTRODUCTION

This erratum aims to point out that our previous claim from [1], regarding the additivity of κ -entanglement in Eq. (9) therein, is not correct. As a result of this finding and previous ones from [1], the regularized κ -entanglement gives the exact entanglement cost under quantum operations that completely preserve positivity of the partial transpose (PPT).

We also point out that a related claim from [2], regarding the additivity of the κ -entanglement of quantum channels, is not correct. We then show various bounds on the exact parallel and sequential simulation cost of quantum channels, in terms of the κ -entanglement of quantum channels and its regularization.

II. κ -ENTANGLEMENT FOR STATES

For the κ -entanglement [1], its primal semidefinite program (SDP) is defined as

$$E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}) := \log_2 \inf_{S_{AB} \geq 0} \{ \text{Tr}[S_{AB}] : -S_{AB}^{T_B} \leq \rho_{AB}^{T_B} \leq S_{AB}^{T_B} \}, \quad (1)$$

and its dual SDP is given by

$$E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}) := \sup \{ \log_2 \text{Tr} \rho_{AB} (V_{AB} - W_{AB}) : V_{AB} + W_{AB} \leq \mathbb{1}_{AB}, V_{AB}^{T_B}, W_{AB}^{T_B} \geq 0 \}. \quad (2)$$

We note that Ref. [1] already proved that strong duality holds, so that the primal and dual expressions are equal.

Proposition 1 *The κ -entanglement is only subadditive, obeying*

$$E_\kappa(\rho_{A_1B_1} \otimes \theta_{A_2B_2}) \leq E_\kappa(\rho_{A_1B_1}) + E_\kappa(\theta_{A_2B_2}), \quad (3)$$

for states $\rho_{A_1B_1}$ and $\theta_{A_2B_2}$, and it is not additive in general, contrary to the claim of [1, Eq. (9)].

Proof. The subadditivity follows from the primal SDP (cf. Eq. (1)) of κ -entanglement, and it has already been proved in the published version of [1]. However, superadditivity of κ -entanglement does not hold as previously claimed, due to the following counterexample.

Specifically, let us consider the following bipartite two-qutrit state:

$$\omega_{AB} := \frac{3}{5}|v_0\rangle\langle v_0| + \frac{3}{10}|v_1\rangle\langle v_1| + \frac{1}{10}|v_2\rangle\langle v_2|, \quad (4)$$

with

$$|v_0\rangle := \frac{3}{5}|00\rangle + \frac{2}{5}|01\rangle + \frac{3}{5}|02\rangle - \frac{1}{5}|11\rangle + \frac{1}{5}|12\rangle - \frac{1}{5}|22\rangle, \quad (5)$$

$$|v_1\rangle := \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|11\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|12\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|20\rangle, \quad (6)$$

$$|v_2\rangle := \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}|00\rangle - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}|01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}|11\rangle - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}|20\rangle - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}|21\rangle. \quad (7)$$

For the state ω_{AB} , the following inequality holds:

$$2E_\kappa(\omega_{AB}) - E_\kappa(\omega_{AB}^{\otimes 2}) > 2 \times 0.6097607 - 1.2192754 > 0.00024. \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the κ -entanglement E_κ is not additive under tensor products. We note that the computation above is implemented by CVX (a Matlab package for disciplined convex programming), whose codes are provided as arXiv ancillary files. ■

Let us remark here that another counterexample to additivity of κ -entanglement was found independently in Ref. [3], which also points out the following necessity of regularizing the exact entanglement cost.

Previously, Theorem 1 of [1] stated that the exact entanglement cost under PPT operations is given by the κ -entanglement. However, due to the non-additivity of κ -entanglement from Proposition 1 above, we now only have that the regularized κ -entanglement characterizes the exact entanglement cost under PPT operations.

Theorem 2 *(Revised version of Theorem 1 in [1]) The PPT exact entanglement cost of an arbitrary bipartite state ρ_{AB} is given by the regularized κ -entanglement, i.e.,*

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) = E_\kappa^\infty(\rho_{AB}) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}^{\otimes n})}{n}. \quad (9)$$

Proof. Note that the one-shot exact entanglement cost under PPT operations is bounded by the κ -entanglement [1, Proposition 2] as follows:

$$\log_2(2^{E_\kappa(\rho_{AB})} - 1) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}^{(1)}(\rho_{AB}) \leq \log_2(2^{E_\kappa(\rho_{AB})} + 2). \quad (10)$$

Hence, the asymptotic exact entanglement cost under PPT operations is upper bounded as follows:

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_{\text{PPT}}^{(1)}(\rho_{AB}^{\otimes n}) \quad (11)$$

$$\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log(2^{E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}^{\otimes n})} + 2) \quad (12)$$

$$= E_\kappa^\infty(\rho_{AB}). \quad (13)$$

Similarly, we have

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) \geq E_\kappa^\infty(\rho_{AB}), \quad (14)$$

thus concluding the proof. ■

It was claimed in [1, Eq. (11)] that the exact entanglement cost under PPT operations, $E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB})$, is additive; however, this claim no longer holds because it relied on additivity of κ -entanglement. It remains an open question to determine whether $E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB})$ is additive or not.

In [4], Lami introduced the following variant of κ -entanglement, E_χ , defined by

$$E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) := \sup\{\log_2 \text{Tr} \rho_{AB}(V_{AB} - W_{AB}) : -\mathbb{1}_{AB} \leq V_{AB} + W_{AB} \leq \mathbb{1}_{AB}, V_{AB}^{T_B}, W_{AB}^{T_B} \geq 0\}, \quad (15)$$

and he also suggested that it would be additive. Let us note here that constructing additive quantities in this way is standard by now and has appeared numerous times in previous literature on defining SDP bounds for operational quantities of interest (see, e.g., [5, Eqs. (3.17), (4.8), (5.94), (5.99)]). As also observed in [4], the above optimization problem requires one more constraint than the original κ -entanglement, which implies that

$$E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) \leq E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}), \quad \forall \rho_{AB}. \quad (16)$$

In what follows, we prove that E_χ is indeed superadditive (cf. Prop. 3) and so useful in lower bounding the exact entanglement cost under PPT operations (cf. Theorem 4). Note that this superadditivity is in contrast to the κ -entanglement.

Proposition 3 *For two bipartite states ρ_{AB} and $\omega_{A'B'}$ acting on separable Hilbert spaces, the following superadditivity inequality holds:*

$$E_\chi(\rho_{AB} \otimes \omega_{A'B'}) \geq E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) + E_\chi(\omega_{A'B'}). \quad (17)$$

where the bipartition on the left-hand side is understood as $AA'|BB'$.

Proof. Let $\{V_{AB}^1, W_{AB}^1\}$ and $\{V_{A'B'}^2, W_{A'B'}^2\}$ be arbitrary operators satisfying the conditions in Eq. (15) for ρ_{AB} and $\omega_{A'B'}$, respectively. Now we choose

$$R_{ABA'B'} = V_{AB}^1 \otimes V_{A'B'}^2 + W_{AB}^1 \otimes W_{A'B'}^2, \quad (18)$$

$$S_{ABA'B'} = V_{AB}^1 \otimes W_{A'B'}^2 + W_{AB}^1 \otimes V_{A'B'}^2. \quad (19)$$

One can verify from (15) and [6, Lemma 12.35] that

$$R_{ABA'B'}^{T_{BB'}} + S_{ABA'B'}^{T_{BB'}} \geq 0, \quad (20)$$

$$R_{ABA'B'} + S_{ABA'B'} = (V_{AB}^1 + W_{AB}^1) \otimes (V_{AB}^2 + W_{AB}^2) \leq \mathbf{1}_{ABA'B'}, \quad (21)$$

$$R_{ABA'B'} + S_{ABA'B'} = (V_{AB}^1 + W_{AB}^1) \otimes (V_{AB}^2 + W_{AB}^2) \geq -\mathbf{1}_{ABA'B'}, \quad (22)$$

which implies that $\{R_{ABA'B'}, S_{ABA'B'}\}$ is a feasible solution to (15) for $E_\chi(\rho_{AB} \otimes \omega_{A'B'})$. Thus, we have that

$$E_\chi(\rho_{AB} \otimes \omega_{A'B'}) \geq \log_2 \text{Tr}(\rho_{AB} \otimes \omega_{A'B'})(R_{ABA'B'} - S_{ABA'B'}) \quad (23)$$

$$= \log_2[\text{Tr} \rho_{AB}(V_{AB}^1 - W_{AB}^1) \cdot \text{Tr} \omega_{A'B'}(V_{A'B'}^2 - W_{A'B'}^2)] \quad (24)$$

$$= \log_2(\text{Tr} \rho_{AB}(V_{AB}^1 - W_{AB}^1)) + \log_2(\text{Tr} \omega_{A'B'}(V_{A'B'}^2 - W_{A'B'}^2)). \quad (25)$$

Since the inequality has been shown for arbitrary $\{V_{AB}^1, W_{AB}^1\}$ and $\{V_{A'B'}^2, W_{A'B'}^2\}$ satisfying the conditions in (15) for ρ_{AB} and $\omega_{A'B'}$, respectively, we conclude that $E_\chi(\rho_{AB} \otimes \omega_{A'B'}) \geq E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) + E_\chi(\omega_{A'B'})$. ■

Theorem 4 For every bipartite state ρ_{AB} , the following inequalities hold:

$$E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) \leq E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}). \quad (26)$$

Proof. First, we apply the subadditivity of E_κ to show that

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}^{\otimes n})}{n} \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{nE_\kappa(\rho_{AB})}{n} = E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}). \quad (27)$$

Second, we apply (16) and the superadditivity of E_χ (Proposition 3) to show that

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}^{\otimes n})}{n} \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{E_\chi(\rho_{AB}^{\otimes n})}{n} \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{nE_\chi(\rho_{AB})}{n} = E_\chi(\rho_{AB}). \quad (28)$$

Therefore, we have that $E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) \leq E_\kappa(\rho_{AB})$. ■

Corollary 5 For every bipartite state ρ_{AB} satisfying $E_\chi(\rho_{AB}) = E_\kappa(\rho_{AB})$, the following equalities hold:

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}) = E_\kappa(\rho_{AB}) = E_\chi(\rho_{AB}). \quad (29)$$

In [1], it was claimed that exact PPT entanglement manipulation is irreversible. By considering the example given there, and applying Corollary 5, we confirm that $E_{\text{PPT}}(\rho_{AB}^\nu) = 1$, as claimed, for the state ρ_{AB}^ν defined in [1, Eq. (15)].

III. κ -ENTANGLEMENT FOR CHANNELS

Similar issues apply to the κ -entanglement of quantum channels, as defined in [2]. Therein, the κ -entanglement of a channel $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ was defined as

$$E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) := \inf_{Q_{AB} \geq 0} \left\{ \log_2 \|\text{Tr}_B[Q_{AB}]\|_\infty : -Q_{AB}^{T_B} \leq (J_{AB}^\mathcal{N})^{T_B} \leq Q_{AB}^{T_B} \right\}, \quad (30)$$

where $J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}}$ is the Choi operator of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$:

$$J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}} := \sum_{i,j} |i\rangle\langle j|_A \otimes \mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}(|i\rangle\langle j|). \quad (31)$$

The dual SDP of $E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ is given by

$$E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = \sup_{V_{AB}^T, W_{AB}^T, \rho_A \geq 0} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \log_2 \text{Tr}[J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}}(V_{AB} - W_{AB})] : \\ V_{AB} + W_{AB} \leq \rho_A \otimes I_B, \text{Tr}[\rho_A] = 1 \end{array} \right\}. \quad (32)$$

Ref. [2] proved that strong duality holds, so that the primal and dual expressions are equal.

For similar reasons as before, the claimed additivity proof for $E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ in [2, Proposition 11] does not hold. Instead, only the following subadditivity inequality holds for two channels $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}$:

$$E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B} \otimes \mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}) \leq E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) + E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}), \quad (33)$$

as shown in the first part of the proof of [2, Proposition 11]. We have also found a numerical counterexample to the additivity of κ -entanglement of quantum channels, and the code and data files needed to reconstruct this counterexample are available as arXiv ancillary files.

The operational quantity known as the exact parallel entanglement cost of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ under PPT operations is defined as

$$E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) := \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_{\text{PPT}}^{(1)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}^{\otimes n}), \quad (34)$$

where $E_{\text{PPT}}^{(1)}$ is defined in [2, Eq. (118)]. Previously, Theorem 17 of [2] stated that $E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ is given by the κ -entanglement of channels. However, due to the gap in the proof of additivity, we now only have that the regularized κ -entanglement of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ characterizes the exact parallel entanglement cost of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$:

Theorem 6 (Revised version of Theorem 17 in [2]) *Let $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ be a quantum channel. Then the exact parallel entanglement cost of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ under PPT operations is equal to the regularized κ -entanglement:*

$$E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_{\kappa}^{\infty}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}^{\otimes n}). \quad (35)$$

Proof. Consider the following one-shot bound from Proposition 16 of [2]:

$$\log_2(2^{E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})} - 1) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}^{(1)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq \log_2(2^{E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})} + 2). \quad (36)$$

Applying this and the definition of $E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ in (34), we find that

$$E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_{\text{PPT}}^{(1)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}^{\otimes n}) \quad (37)$$

$$\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2(2^{E_{\kappa}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}^{\otimes n})} + 2) \quad (38)$$

$$= E_{\kappa}^{\infty}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}). \quad (39)$$

Similarly, we have

$$E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \geq E_{\kappa}^{\infty}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}), \quad (40)$$

thus concluding the proof. ■

Previously, Theorem 19 of [2] stated that the exact sequential channel simulation cost of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$, denoted by $E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ and defined in Section IV-B of [2], is equal to its κ -entanglement. However, again due to the fact that additivity does not hold, we now only have bounds on this quantity. Furthermore, Proposition 18 of [2] needs to be slightly revised, because it did not take into account the precise form of the upper bound in Proposition 16 of [2]. Let us first present the following revision of Proposition 18 of [2], which involves the n -shot exact sequential simulation cost $E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}, n)$, as defined in [2, Eq. (163)]:

Proposition 7 (Revised version of Proposition 18 of [2]) *Let $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ be a quantum channel such that $E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) > 0$. Then the n -shot exact sequential simulation cost is bounded as*

$$\log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}^{\otimes n})} - 1 \right] \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}, n) \leq \log_2 \left[2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right]. \quad (41)$$

Proof. The proof of the lower bound is exactly the same as before, but we do not invoke superadditivity since it does not hold. The revised steps for the proof of the upper bound are as follows. By the one-shot upper bound from Proposition 16 of [2], the cost $\log_2 M_{n-1}$ is bounded as

$$\log_2 M_{n-1} \leq \log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \right]. \quad (42)$$

See [2, Eqs. (184)–(185)] for the definition of M_{n-1} . The cost $\log_2 M_{n-2}$ of the $n - 1$ simulation is then bounded as

$$\log_2 M_{n-2} \leq \log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N} \otimes \text{id}^{M_{n-1}})} + 2 \right] \quad (43)$$

$$\leq \log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}) + \log_2 M_{n-1}} + 2 \right] \quad (44)$$

$$= \log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} M_{n-1} + 2 \right] \quad (45)$$

$$\leq \log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} (2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2) + 2 \right] \quad (46)$$

$$= \log_2 \left[2^{2E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \sum_{\ell=0}^1 2^{\ell E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} \right]. \quad (47)$$

Performing this kind of reasoning iteratively, going backward until the first simulation, we find the following bound:

$$\log_2 M_0 \leq \log_2 \left[2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \sum_{\ell=0}^{n-1} 2^{\ell E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} \right] = \log_2 \left[2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right]. \quad (48)$$

This concludes the proof. ■

We then have the following revision of Theorem 19 therein:

Theorem 8 (Revised version of Theorem 19 of [2]) *Let $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ be a quantum channel. Then the exact sequential channel simulation cost of $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ is bounded as follows:*

$$E_\kappa^\infty(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}). \quad (49)$$

Proof. The lower bound follows from the lower bound in (41) and the following reasoning:

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}, n) \quad (50)$$

$$\geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}^{\otimes n})} - 1 \right] \quad (51)$$

$$= E_\kappa^\infty(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}). \quad (52)$$

The upper bound follows from the upper bound in (41) and the following reasoning:

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}, n) \quad (53)$$

$$\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right] \quad (54)$$

$$\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2 \cdot 2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} + 2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right] \quad (55)$$

$$= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2 \cdot 2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} \left(\frac{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right] \quad (56)$$

$$= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2 \left(\frac{2^{(n+1)E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})}}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right] \quad (57)$$

$$= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2 \left(\frac{2^{(n+1)E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1}{2^{E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 1} \right) \right] \quad (58)$$

$$= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \log_2 \left[2 \left(\frac{2^{nE_\kappa(\mathcal{N})} - 2^{-E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})}}{1 - 2^{-E_\kappa(\mathcal{N})}} \right) \right] \quad (59)$$

$$= E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}), \quad (60)$$

concluding the proof. ■

Let us introduce the following variant of κ -entanglement of a channel, E_χ , defined by

$$E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) := \sup_{V_{AB}^{TB}, W_{AB}^{TB}, \rho_A \geq 0} \left\{ \log_2 \text{Tr}[J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}}(V_{AB} - W_{AB})] : \begin{array}{l} -\rho_A \otimes I_B \leq V_{AB} + W_{AB} \leq \rho_A \otimes I_B, \\ \text{Tr}[\rho_A] = 1 \end{array} \right\}. \quad (61)$$

It is a channel generalization of the quantity defined in (15). This optimization problem requires one more constraint than the original κ -entanglement, implying that

$$E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}), \quad \forall \mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}. \quad (62)$$

In what follows, we prove that $E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ is superadditive, and so it is useful in bounding both the parallel and sequential simulation costs from below.

Proposition 9 *For all channels $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}$, the following superadditivity inequality holds:*

$$E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B} \otimes \mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}) \geq E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) + E_\chi(\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}). \quad (63)$$

Proof. To see the superadditivity of E_χ for quantum channels, let us suppose that $\{V_{AB}^1, W_{AB}^1, \rho_A^1\}$ and $\{V_{A'B'}^2, W_{A'B'}^2, \rho_{A'}^2\}$ are arbitrary operators satisfying the conditions in (61) for $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}$, respectively. Now we choose

$$R_{ABA'B'} = V_{AB}^1 \otimes V_{A'B'}^2 + W_{AB}^1 \otimes W_{A'B'}^2, \quad (64)$$

$$S_{ABA'B'} = V_{AB}^1 \otimes W_{A'B'}^2 + W_{AB}^1 \otimes V_{A'B'}^2. \quad (65)$$

One can verify from (61) and [6, Lemma 12.35] that

$$R_{ABA'B'}^{T_{BB'}} \geq 0, \quad (66)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\rho_A^1 \otimes \rho_{A'}^2 \otimes I_{BB'} &\leq R_{ABA'B'} + S_{ABA'B'} = (V_{AB}^1 + W_{AB}^1) \otimes (V_{A'B'}^2 + W_{A'B'}^2) \\ &\leq \rho_A^1 \otimes \rho_{A'}^2 \otimes I_{BB'}, \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

which implies that $\{R_{ABA'B'}, S_{ABA'B'}, \rho_A^1 \otimes \rho_{A'}^2\}$ is feasible for $E_{\kappa'}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B} \otimes \mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'})$ in (61). Thus, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B} \otimes \mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}) &\geq \log_2 \text{Tr}(J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}} \otimes J_{A'B'}^{\mathcal{M}})(R_{ABA'B'} - S_{ABA'B'}) \\ &= \log_2[\text{Tr} J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}}(V_{AB}^1 - W_{AB}^1) \cdot \text{Tr} J_{A'B'}^{\mathcal{M}}(V_{A'B'}^2 - W_{A'B'}^2)] \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

$$= \log_2[\text{Tr} J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}}(V_{AB}^1 - W_{AB}^1) \cdot \text{Tr} J_{A'B'}^{\mathcal{M}}(V_{A'B'}^2 - W_{A'B'}^2)] \quad (69)$$

$$= \log_2(\text{Tr} J_{AB}^{\mathcal{N}}(V_{AB}^1 - W_{AB}^1)) + \log_2(\text{Tr} J_{A'B'}^{\mathcal{M}}(V_{A'B'}^2 - W_{A'B'}^2)). \quad (70)$$

Since the inequality has been shown for arbitrary $\{V_{AB}^1, W_{AB}^1, \rho_A^1\}$ and $\{V_{A'B'}^2, W_{A'B'}^2, \rho_{A'}^2\}$ satisfying the conditions in (61) for $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}$, respectively, we conclude that

$$E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B} \otimes \mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}) \geq E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) + E_\chi(\mathcal{M}_{A' \rightarrow B'}), \quad (71)$$

which completes the proof. ■

Theorem 10 For every channel $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$, the following inequalities hold:

$$E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}). \quad (72)$$

Proof. Applying (35), (62), and Proposition 9, it follows that

$$E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_\kappa^\infty(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \quad (73)$$

$$= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}^{\otimes n}) \quad (74)$$

$$\geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}^{\otimes n}) \quad (75)$$

$$\geq E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}). \quad (76)$$

The inequality $E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ follows from definitions, and the inequality $E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$ was already established above in (49). ■

Corollary 11 For every channel $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ satisfying $E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B})$, the following equalities hold:

$$E_\chi(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_\kappa(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}). \quad (77)$$

We finally require the following revisions:

Theorem 12 (Revision of Theorem 20 of [2]) *Let $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ be a PPT-simulable channel with associated resource state $\omega_{A'B'}$. Then the PPT-assisted entanglement cost of a channel is bounded from above as*

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) \leq E_{\text{PPT}}(\omega_{A'B'}) = E_{\kappa}^{\infty}(\omega_{A'B'}). \quad (78)$$

Theorem 13 (Revision of Theorem 21 of [2]) *Let $\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}$ be a PPT-simulable channel with associated resource state $\omega_{A'B'}$. Suppose furthermore that it is resource-seizable, as given in Definition 5 of [2]. Then*

$$E_{\text{PPT}}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_{\text{PPT}}^{(p)}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_{\kappa}^{\infty}(\mathcal{N}_{A \rightarrow B}) = E_{\text{PPT}}(\omega_{A'B'}) = E_{\kappa}^{\infty}(\omega_{A'B'}). \quad (79)$$

A final adjustment is needed around Eq. (239) of [2], regarding the simulation cost of the amplitude damping channel. Since this channel is a qubit-input, qubit-output channel, its κ -entanglement is indeed additive as claimed, as a consequence of [2, Remark 2].

Acknowledgement. We thank Ludovico Lami for notifying us [4] that there is a gap in the proof of [1, Theorem 1], which claimed additivity of κ -entanglement. We also thank Ludovico Lami and Bartosz Regula for notifying us [3] of their independently found counterexample to additivity of κ -entanglement.

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